

Environmental, Agricultural & Social Informatics Specializations and its Potentialities at Engineering Degrees - An Indian Context

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ABSTRACT

Informatics is an important field of practice and study. It is very similar and also close to Information Science. Informatics initially only were considered as a branch of advanced applied science but gradually it has become a domain centric field for information and technological solutions. Among the most common and available Informatics nomenclature important are Health Informatics, Bio Informatics, Geo Informatics, etc. The advent of IT and Computing in the field of Environmental Sciences and the whole sector leads Environmental Informatics as an important interdisciplinary field of studies and practice for environmental monitoring and solutions leading to the environmental management, disaster management, agricultural management. Therefore, universities and educational institutions are moving towards academic programs on environmental informatics and allied fields. Similar to Environmental Informatics another sub field also gaining popularity i.e., Agricultural Informatics and this is incorporated with the technology and management also. The subject is being offered at different level for the best environmental solutions. Moreover, another important domain centric Informatics field also becomes important i.e., Social Informatics which is dedicated to social applications using Information Technology and allied systems. Social Informatics is also concern about the Urban and Rural Development with the Urban and Rural Informatics. This paper is a theoretical study on Environmental, Agricultural, and Social Informatics with reference to basic features, functions, and applications.

Keywords: *Informatics, IT, Environmental Informatics, Emerging Technologies, Agricultural Informatics, Educational Systems*

1. INTRODUCTION

Informatics becomes one of the important subjects with various interdisciplinary components. This is moreover responsible for information solutions ranging from collection, selection, organization, processing, management, and dissemination. Informatics is also called Information Science is with ample opportunities in information and technological solutions [1], [5], [30]. In many countries, Informatics is also called Information Science. Initially, only the Informatics field was started and gained popularity due to its wider applications and areas. Later different kinds of domain based Informatics or Information Science also gained popularity and among these important are as follows-

- Bio Informatics
- Geo Informatics
- Health Informatics
- Business Informatics
- Chem Informatics, etc.

Even the gradual development of such Informatics led to the development of many other new areas and Informatics such as Public Health Informatics, Dental Informatics, Nursing Informatics, Security Informatics, Irrigation Informatics, Design Informatics, Ecological Informatics, Agricultural

Informatics, Social Informatics, etc. The growing role of Informatics in Environment, Ecology, and Disaster Management lead the development of another interdisciplinary subject called Environmental Informatics. Similarly, the growing need of ICT, and Informatics in Agriculture results in another important subject called Agricultural Informatics. It is about agricultural precision management, technological empowerment with agricultural products and services [7], [27], [36].

In the segment of emerging Informatics, another important area is Social Informatics which is the application of ICT, IT, and Computing in Society, Social Development and Sciences. Therefore, this subject is also rising not only in Developed countries but also in Developing Countries.

2. ENVIRONMENTAL INFORMATICS: THE ROOT FOR ENVIRONMENTAL DEVELOPMENT & SUSTAINABILITY

As an interdisciplinary subject, Environmental Informatics is not only to solve the problem of the environment but also for some other allied areas and fields such as agriculture, geology, oceanography, climatology, ecology, biology, zoology, soil science, atmospheric sciences, physics, chemistry, etc. Environmental Informatics is also known as Ecological Informatics and Eco Informatics. The field is related to Green Technology, Green ICT in some context. Environmental Informatics is an Applied Science and therefore responsible for different environmental, ecological solutions, environmental management, and development, etc [9], [26], [40]. In a broader context, it is dedicated to the following-

- Environmental Informatics is dedicated to proper managing of energy, environmental, ecological systems as well as its promotion in better and healthy way.
- The field is also required in the promotion of Environmental decision making including for its better Simulation, optimization and efficiency with better utilization of the environment.
- Environmental Informatics is related to the Agricultural Informatics, Ecological Informatics, Geo Informatics directly and indirectly and therefore solves the problems of such fields as well. The fig: 1 depicted in brief in this regard [3], [13], [32].

Fig: 1-Related Beneficiary fields of Environmental Informatics

- There are many technologies and tools in Environmental Informatics rising rapidly and among these valuables are GIS, Remote Sensing, spatial information technologies, etc. and all these are required in proper sustainable development effectively.

- Environmental chemistry and biochemistry are also getting benefits from the field like Environmental Informatics as well as allied fields and this scenario is rising rapidly.
- Atomic, molecular and macromolecular scales, etc measurable with the Environmental IT practice and it led the development [11], [31], [39].
- In proper and healthy designing, development of the chemical and biological aspects such are related to the environmental processes are also empowered by the Environmental Informatics.
- Modeling of biotechnological aspects including pollution mitigation may be considered as important Environmental Informatics [12], [28].
- As far as Database tools, multimedia tools, graphics, visualization tools, etc are concerned Environmental Informatics may be considered as worthy field which can ultimately help in proper sustainable development.
- Artificial intelligence, expert systems, machine learning, deep learning, etc. are important and valuable in regard to agricultural development with the help of Environmental Informatics practice. Regarding the managerial aspects like statistics and risk analysis related to environmental areas and ecology, Environmental Informatics is worthy.

Therefore, Environmental Informatics is important in direct and indirect benefits to different sectors and subjects like Agriculture, Geology, Oceanography, Climatology, Biology, Zoology, Atmospheric sciences, Physics, Chemistry, Anthropology, etc. Social enhancement and overall development are positively possible with Environmental Informatics [8], [33], [38]. Therefore institutions, organizations and associations are engaged in academic research, degrees, and initiative for further processing of Environmental Informatics practice towards a green world.

3. AGRICULTURAL INFORMATICS: AN OVERVIEW

Agricultural Informatics helps in practicing of agricultural production and further activities by various technologies, methods, tools, etc in farming as well as in various agricultural activities. According to expert cultivation is considered, farming in a small area and ideally consider as the need for a family production only whereas, agriculture is involved in a large place. Moreover, it is considered as a commercial intensive and deals with a variety of components viz. plants, seed and corps, animals, etc with the help of miscellaneous methods and therefore also called as Industrial Agriculture [14], [37]. Information Technology (including informatics and management) applications become a common activity in the recent past in diverse areas of agriculture. However, this branch is also applicable in other areas and allied fields viz. horticulture, veterinary sciences, geography, etc. Technology, Information and management techniques are normally treated as important in healthy and better Agricultural Informatics practice. Information and similar content are treated as important in development activities and in Agriculture also this plays a leading role. In the recent past, Agricultural Informatics has started wide practice in developed countries, and as a result, many universities internationally started programs on Agricultural Informatics. Even in some developing nations also started practicing Agricultural Informatics and the academic programs on this very relevant branch [19], [38]. Apart from the Agricultural Informatics nomenclature, it is started in other domains viz.—

- Agricultural Information Technology,
- Agricultural Information Systems
- Smart Agriculture
- Agricultural Data Sciences, etc.

This trend is in Agricultural Informatics and allied areas are going on rapid stage in many institutions in the current past.

4. AGRICULTURAL INFORMATICS: THE FOUNDATION, FEATURES AND NATURE

Informatics is the study and practice of information collection, selection, organization, processing, management, dissemination, and allied activities. Various kinds of IT components are strongly associated with Informatics viz. database technologies, networking technologies, web technologies, multimedia technologies, etc. Hence all these are applicable in Agricultural field and makes

Informatics/ Information Science as an important field of study and practice. It is importantly an emerging subject and started in many international universities. At the beginning, Agricultural Documentation was considered as the field but gradually other branches have been emerged [6], [15], [35]. This branch deals with various features and among such few important are—

- Agricultural Informatics is mostly interdisciplinary and therefore it also helps in other allied subjects like *horticulture, veterinary sciences, ecology, Computer Science, Computer Engineering, IT, Information Science, etc.*
- The field of Agricultural Informatics is also called as Agro ICT or Agro Information Technology and therefore it inherits the technological, social, ecological aspects. Furthermore, it also enlightens agro business and therefore helps in Managerial and Commercial, activities.
- Information or knowledge or data is needful and practiced in Agricultural activities including pre and post production of Agricultural works, this field becomes useful.
- Due to nature and key job/ roles, this is become an important subject in Engineering Sciences become an important subject.
- Computational systems/ technologies are considered as important in Agricultural Informatics practice and it ultimately helps in enhancing and developing smart agricultural systems empowered by the technologies.
- Various latest sub technologies like Cloud Computing and Technologies, Robotics and AI, Green Computing and Systems, Data Analytics, etc are playing an important role in healthy Agricultural Informatics practice.
- Agricultural Informatics is dedicated to proper societal development and promotion in different means and therefore it holds the nature of social sciences as well.
- Ecology is also associated with Agricultural Informatics and it is needed in better, healthy and natural farm management and complete sustainable development.
- Most of the Agricultural activities are these days technology dependent and also lie on management, etc. The technologies of Agricultural Informatics are also changing and becoming more advanced and socially touched.

Agricultural Informatics is the need of the hour in healthy Agricultural practices, though it has certain issues and challenges viz. shortage in proper awareness, policy framework, governmental supports, proper educational policies, research and training initiatives, etc. Therefore, ultimately Agricultural Informatics/ Agro ICT leads the development of agriculture and agricultural sectors effectively [4], [17].

5. SOCIAL INFORMATICS: OVERVIEW, FEATURES, AND FUNCTIONS

Social Informatics is another form of Informatics with a role in developing IT and Computing practices in societal activities; this is dedicated to application, utilization of Information and related technologies into Society (as depicted in Fig: 2). Historically societal stages and advance Society in today's context lies on information and technology related systems. Social Informatics today is deemed as technological involvement and here information transfer and technology transfer play a critical role. It is an interdisciplinary study of uses, design and consequences of IT in the context of society and community [2], [23], [34]. The following may be considered as valuable characteristics as far as social informatics is concerned.

- This is the trans-disciplinary field and many ways help in developing Socio-economic development.
- Social Informatics is dedicated in effective information systems development, since it brings Technology and Society together; and composes ICT based systems [6], [18].
- Social Informatics is the study of social aspects of computerization and simply it is the IT uses in society, community and organizations. Therefore, it has wider contribution in social as well as cultural practices.
- Social Informatics as a field of study not so much popular yet in developing countries and further as far as technologies are concerned it is the application of the Deductive Method.

Social Informatics is a broad field and indirectly connected with Agricultural Informatics, Environmental Informatics, Geo Informatics. According to the expert, these indirect areas may also be called as sub-field of Social Informatics. Some of the important sub component or fields of Social Informatics are included Urban Informatics and Rural Informatics.

Urban Informatics is dedicated in the development of ICT applications in the urbanization, urban development, and responsible for examining day-to-day issues of the towns, cities, and including its natives. In town planning, city management, disaster management, traffic management also Urban Informatics can be considered as worthy. The latest and emerging technologies such as HCI, Data Science, Big Data, Cloud Computing, AI & Robotics also perform a leading role in the context of Urban Informatics practice and development [24], [25].

Fig: 2-Technological role in changes in social systems powered by Social Informatics

Urban Informatics is about the gathering, analyzing, and interaction of information for the better urban practice and powered by the technologies to their citizens. It is the study of the people generating and using ICT [10], [20], [21]. Urban Informatics stakeholders are normally treated as-

- People,
- Place, and
- Technology.

It is also deals with the geographic and spatial data related activities ranging from the *Governmental data such as census data, open data, etc., proper and healthy Personal data, Sensor data, such as transport, surveillance, CCTV, etc.* According to the experts in the year 1987, urban informatics term was coined but gained popularity as a field of study in 2006. Later gradually emerging technologies like ubiquitous computing, open data and big data analytics, emerged for perfect development [22], [29], [36].

Rural Informatics is another area or sub field of Social Informatics. This is simply the application of Informatics or IT in the areas of Rural Development including for the rural up-gradation and modernization. Development of the rural areas & Social Sector as a whole depends on ICT in many contexts and in this context Rural Informatics plays a leading role. ICT has great potential in rural

development viz. people, services, information and other technologies. ICT applications are empowered opportunities by improving markets, health and education.

6. CONCLUSION

The field of Informatics is gaining popularity in different fields and in this context, all the emerging Informatics domains mentioned in this work can be considered as worthy. Environmental Informatics is associated with environmental engineering; therefore, it can be helpful in organizations, governments, foundations, and associations to get wider Computational and Technological benefits. Information Technology powered by emerging technologies viz. Cloud Computing, Big Data, Analytics, Human Computer Interaction, Usability Systems, 3D and Graphics not only for important in the environment and allied activities but also in Social Development at the large, moreover in Agricultural Development by another focus of Informatics i.e., Agricultural Informatics. Therefore, in all the areas of society, environment and agricultural sectors and development Informatics play a leading role in sustainable development and growth. Academic institutions, organizations, government bodies need proper steps in respect of initiation of academic, training, and research programs and degrees on these emerging and worthy fields of study.

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